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Design of Resilient Smart Systems for Sustainable Cities and Communities

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Abstract: Smart systems are appearing in everyday life. For example, smart phones and smart watches. They ease the task of the user in a several ways. In the similar line, the design of smart systems for rural and urban area can contribute the sustainable development for the communities. The smart system includes smart water conservation and management systems, smart traffic lights, smart street lights, smart bus stops, smart tilt detection of pole, trees and buildings, smart drainage management system, smart roads, smart toll booths on highways, smart farming, smart homes, smart vehicles and green buildings. The paper presents the practical implementation of the resilient digital smart bus stop with real time information for passenger as well as weather. The case study of the rural area has been taken up, it has been shown to be effective for sustainable communities. The paper also demonstrates the simulation and implementation of smart drinking water leakage detection system using computer vision approach. In this case, the waste of water has been detected and corrected by smart mechanism. Thus, making the sustainable water distribution system.

These two cases highlight the sustainability of the smart cities further with using Internet of Things and use of ambient energy for powering the devices. The use of new and renewable energy for such smart systems will make them sustainable for the future cities. The solar, wind, thermal, RF and other modes of energy could be effectively used in the development. The development in the field of the Internet of Things and Machine to Machine communication has open up new avenues for the interconnected world. These leads to cyber physical system, physical mobile satellite systems and cyber physical social system. In the sustainable cities the Satellite based Internet of Things (SIoT) are going to play the significant role in developing smart cities using LEO satellites.

Keywords: Smart System, Internet of Things, Digital Infrastructure, Smart Bus Stop, Smart Water Leakage Detection and Sustainable Cities, M2M Communication.

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Main Highlights : The work presented here highlights the resilient smart systems for sustainable cities and communities. It has been demonstrated with implementation of smart bus pick up stand, smart traffic light, smart street light and smart water leakage detection system for sustainable cities and communities. The designed, developed and implemented systems have remained resilient and effective in operation and supports in information dissemination, avoiding traffic congestion, effective use of power and conservation of water which are key for smart cities and sustainable developments.

1. Introduction

The need of the time is to design and implement the smart things for rural and urban areas of the country. The smart things facilitate coordination and automation among several connected things. The development in the field of the Internet of Things and Machine to Machine communication has open up new avenues for the interconnected world. In the developed nation smart things exist and are in use since long which shows sustainability and effectiveness to the society making the life easier. In the country, rural areas are gradually becoming well connected to nearby town and city. This brings the technology specifically construction technology and information technology. Design of green buildings and surroundings space with solar trees for solar energy harvesting is fetching attention of the administration and society. This is required for sustainable development. The smart things generally focus on energy savings, time savings, comfortable execution of task, managing population density and effectively including electronic and information automation through wireless communication technology and mobile communication technology. In the regard design of internet of things for the various application brings in a component of smartness into the system. As mentioned earlier, Design of smart things requires the electronics, information and communication technology, civil engineering and mechanical engineering domain expertise. In this paper, design outline of smart things such as smart bus pick up stand, smart traffic signal lights, smart street light, and smart water conservation system [1] are presented.

2. Novelty of Applications Described

The paper presents a novel, interdisciplinary approach to designing **smart systems for sustainable development**, particularly focusing on rural and urban communities. The key innovations include:

Smart Bus Pick-Up Stand

- Real-time passenger information via **RF modules, GPS/NavIC tracking, and solar-powered displays.**
- Integration of **IoT, Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, surveillance cameras,** and renewable energy.

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- Concept of “**Internet of Inverter (IoI)**” for power health monitoring is innovative.

Smart Traffic Light Controller

- **Computer vision** based traffic monitoring using cameras.
- Wireless communication via **LoRa/LoRaWAN** for efficient and low-power remote control.
- "Internet of Traffic Lights" concept through remote monitoring dashboard.

Smart Street Light

- Uses **LDRs or solar panels** to sense ambient light and adjust lamp intensity.
- Proposed local or central controller for coordination.
- Integrates **energy conservation** and automation.

Smart Water Leakage Detection

- Unique **camera-based computer vision system** for detecting open taps and leakage.
- Uses stored image patterns and real-time alerts via LEDs.
- Implemented in a **real-world institutional setting in Gujarat, India**.

3. Methodology

The methodology follows a design-thinking and systems engineering approach, including conceptualization, hardware integration, communication protocol selection, and energy management.

Step 1: Problem Identification

- Analyze inefficiencies in transportation, street lighting, and water usage in rural and urban areas.

Step 2: System Design & Architecture

Each smart system is designed with:

- **Sensors and Actuators:** For detection and interaction (e.g., cameras, LDRs, flow sensors).
- **Microcontrollers and Communication Modules:** Integration of GPS, RF, GSM, LoRa/LoRaWAN, and Wi-Fi.
- **Energy Modules:** Solar panels with Off-Grid/Hybrid inverter systems, supported by IoI for monitoring.

Step 3: Data Acquisition & Control

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- For traffic and bus systems, GPS and RF are used for live tracking.
- For water leakage, image databases are created and processed using computer vision algorithms.

Step 4: Display and Alert Mechanism

- LED/LCD panels for public displays.
- Dashboards for monitoring by authorities.
- LED alerts in the event of leak or anomaly detection.

Step 5: Simulation and Prototype Development

- Preliminary simulation using graphical visualization tools (esp. in water leakage).
- Real-time implementation in institutional environments for validation.

Step 6: Sustainability Integration

- Use of **solar energy**, **IoT-enabled power inverters**, and minimal power protocols like LoRa for energy efficiency.

4. SMART BUS PICK UP STAND:

Figure 1. Smart Bus Pick Up Stand

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Figure 2. Bus Pick Stand proposed to be designed as Smart Stand

Figure 1 demonstrates the smart bus pick up stand in the town area. This stand has digital display for information about bus route, bus arrival time, bus departure time, status of the bus departed. It has an RF module and antenna for communication with bus and control monitoring station.

In Figure 2, the bus pick stand which is proposed to be smart has been shown. On this stand, the present stop name and bus routes are printed. This is quite simple and passenger having knowledge of the arrival time of the bus can arrive at the bus stand wait for a while and board the bus when it arrives. In the mean time, if he is just in time, may not know if the bus is arriving or already departed. For this, bus stand needs to be smart to provide such information for passenger. In addition, feature that this passenger pick up stand would have is solar photovoltaic panel to power the RF module, Antenna (if designed to be active antenna), digital LED display and sensors if nay for example camera or proximity sensors.

4.1 Design Steps for Smart Bus Pick Up Stand

It is very important for passenger to know about the timing of arrival and departure at the bus pick up stand. In order to assure the comfortable travel, the information about bus itinerary should be displayed on the Light Emitting Diode (LED) based display or Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) at the bus pick up stand. In the design, following steps are followed.

Obtaining the timing schedule from the bus operator system, for example Gujarat State Road Transport Corporation (GSRTC) for intra state and interstate transport or Ahmadabad Municipal Corporation (AMC) from Ahmadabad or BEST buses in Mumbai.

- Preloading the timing information about bus arrival and departure information with bus number. This is to done with design of microcontroller board mounted within display panel and mobile application for the data entry about the timing and location information about the stand.
- GPS and /or NavIC [2] based tracking system or terrestrial network (GSM) based design for tracking the bus in real time and providing location information when it reaches to appropriate distance or destination. This digital information provided by tracker needs to be decrypted / decoded using the Application Process Interface [API] for display at the next bus stand and the monitoring station. The server at the designated place can take care of receiving and routing the data. The design is also proposed to connect the server with display using the blue tooth, Zigbee or Wi Fi protocols with digital display.
- The bus pick up stand has been proposed be so designed to be provided with camera for security surveillance and providing real time information at the dashboard of the monitoring authority. This may add the cost but the village or town administration with home department can coordinate it.
- In addition, the power requirements for bus pickup stand are proposed to be provided with solar energy to make it green. The daily generation of the power and utilization of power

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can also be monitored. The OFF grid or ON Grid or Hybrid Design is proposed to be carried out. The appropriate battery with battery management system to be accommodated for OFF grid Design of the system. In the alternate design suggestion, inverter can be connected to the solar panel and ON Grid design can be carried out. As the 4G and 5G connectivity modules are available with Wi-Fi protocol or Mobile data connections, it is possible to monitor the health of the Inverter. This is an Internet of Inverter (IoI), smart inverter. In this present case under proposed design OFF grid system design has been recommended and to match the power requirements with display buck or boost type converter [3],[4] may be used.

- The proposed design can be extended to display the environmental data such as temperature, humidity and other weather forecast. In the present time it is possible to have satellite-based information system at specific place about the bus transportation and environmental sensing as well [5],[6]

Thus, the design of the smart bus pickup stand has been proposed in this work. The details of the technical specification and prototype development are in progress and shall be reported at the conference in future. In this work smart passenger information system at bus pick up stand and digital smart bus pick up stand are used interchangeably at some places.

5. SMART TRAFFIC LIGHT

There are traffic related problems in various towns and cities. There needs to be efficient and effective traffic monitoring system. This task can be accomplished by designing smart traffic light controller. The red, green and yellow signals at cross roads indicate the signal for the vehicle driver to move, wait and stop. Depending upon the traffic flow the signaling can be controlled which is a dynamic system [7].

5.1 Design of Smart Traffic Light Controller

Computer vision-based approach in which image and video signal from camera is proposed to be transmitted to the control room over the wireless terrestrial network (GSM) or LoRa which is a wireless modulation technique derived from Chirp Spread Spectrum (CSS). It encodes information on radio waves using chirp pulses - similar to the way dolphins and bats communicate. LoRa modulated transmission is robust against disturbances and can be received across great distances. LoRaWan is another technique which can be deployed. LoRaWAN is a Media Access Control (MAC) layer protocol built on top of LoRa modulation. It is a software layer which defines how devices use the LoRa hardware, for example when they transmit, and the format of messages. [8]. These signals from four roads of North- South - East- West can be used for decision making about which traffic should be allowed to flow and for how much time. Thus, from the controller room, modulated On- Off signals can be sent which will monitor and control the flow of traffic. This information can be sent over internet, thus, making it Internet of Traffic Lights. The dash board on the control room of the city traffic police department can monitor the traffic. Use of LoRaWan can be advantageous in the following manner,

- **Ultra low power** - LoraWaN end devices are optimized to operate in low power mode and can last up to 10 years on a single coin cell battery.

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- **Long range** - LoRaWAN gateways can transmit and receive signals over a distance of over 10 kilometers in rural areas and up to 3 kilometers in dense urban areas.
- **Deep indoor penetration** - LoRaWAN networks can provide deep indoor coverage, and easily cover multi floor buildings.
- **License free spectrum** - One don't have to pay expensive frequency spectrum license fees to deploy a LoRaWAN network.
- **Geolocation**- A LoRaWAN network can determine the location of end devices using triangulation without the need for GPS. A LoRa end device can be located if at least three gateways pick up its signal.
- **High capacity** - LoRaWAN Network Servers handle millions of messages from thousands of gateways.
- **Public and private deployments** - It is easy to deploy public and private LoRaWAN networks using the same hardware (gateways, end devices, antennas) and software (UDP packet forwarders, Basic Station software, LoRaWAN stacks for end devices).
- **End-to-end security**- LoRaWAN ensures secure communication between end device and the application server using AES-128 encryption.
- **Firmware updates over the air** –

You can remotely update firmware (applications and the LoRaWAN stack) for a single end device or group of end devices.

- **Roaming**- LoRaWAN end devices can perform seamless handovers from **one** network to another. Thus, can cover entire city traffic.

6. SMART STREET LIGHT

In the various rural and urban areas, there needs to design smart street lights those can lit up in the evening when sunsets and turn off when sun rises. When it is midnight, the light intensity is maximum and as the morning starts, the intensity decreases and when complete natural light is visible, it turns it off automatically.[9]

6.1 Design of Smart Street Light Controller

Design of Smart Street light requires the sensors which can be LDR or Solar photovoltaic panel. The output of the sensors changes according to ambient light and sunlight falling on it. This change in the output can be used to map the intensity level of the lamp. The local controller can be used for each of the pole or central controller can be used with connectivity established through wireless seamless or hopping networks, one of which has been discussed with its advantages.

7. SMART WATER CONSERVATION

It is very important for everyone to focus on water conservation. One of the methods used by many organizations and governing is rain water harvesting. Design of the rain water harvesting requires civil engineering works and to make it smart rain water harvesting, rain sensor and flow sensors are required to be placed at several places. Accelerometer meter sensor to be configured as a slope sensor. This designed guided slope can take the rain water in the submersible water tank. Thus, water conservation technique used can monitor the level of the harvested rain water in the well or tank. The water conserved can be used later as a when needed. Such designs can be done for single house, a group of houses and apartments in coordination with gram panchayat, municipal council and municipal corporations.

Another place wherein the water savings needs to be done is at public places and private places. The leakage of water can be detected, monitored and controller. The smart water leakage detection and monitoring is possible by different mechanism. Figure 3, Figure 4 and Figure 5 provides with one of the such mechanism. The designed case was that of the one private engineering institution in the Gujarat. The infrastructure has several drinking water stations. The population in the institution some time keeps the water tap open. Even if the students and staff passing by it noticed the leakage or left the tap open, no action or reaction are given. Thus, camera-based system is designed which used the high-performance graphical simulation and visualization software. The number of image samples were taken and stored in the memory and data base is created. The real-time water leaks or casually left open water tap is detected through camera for various patterns of drop. The decision-making program in the software compares the pattern and flash the LED indicator to the concern administration to take care of the tap and close it. [10]

Figure 3. Smart Water Leakage Detection

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Figure 4. Smart Indication of No drain and drain from drinking water tap

Figure 5. Block diagram for Design of the Smart Water Leakage Monitoring System

8. Analysis with Live Examples

Smart Bus Stop (Live Context)

Use case: A semi-urban bus stop in Gujarat.

- Solar-powered digital displays show real-time bus arrival/departure.
- Reduces waiting time and uncertainty for rural passengers.
- Data pulled from GSRTC or AMC through API integration.

Sustainability Impact:

- Solar energy use reduces grid dependence.
- Enhances rural accessibility and passenger safety.

Smart Traffic Light (Live Simulation)

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Use case: Busy intersections in towns like Mehsana.

- Traffic camera feeds processed using LoRa for signal control.
- Control room dashboard helps in dynamic flow management.

Sustainability Impact:

- Reduces congestion, air pollution.
- Low-power LoRa technology allows for city-wide deployment at low cost.

Smart Street Lighting (Live Environment)

Use case: Villages with no central power grid.

- Lights automatically turn on/off and adjust brightness based on ambient light.
- Street poles connected via mesh network.

Sustainability Impact:

- Massive energy savings.
- Reduces manual effort and ensures 24x7 visibility.

Smart Water Leakage Detection (Institutional Pilot)

Use case: Engineering college in Gujarat.

- Cameras detect running water from taps; triggers alerts if left open.
- Uses image pattern recognition to identify abnormal flow.

Sustainability Impact:

- Saves hundreds of liters of water daily.
- Promotes behavioral change among users.

9 CONCLUDING REMARKS

An attempt has been made to propose the design of smart things for rural and urban areas. There are many other smart things which have been designed and deployed but integration with the local governing council is yet to exist. These things are smart dustbin, smart waste management, smart transportation, smart farming, smart post office, smart elevators and smart apartments. The design has been focused with generalized approach and exact specification and prototype deployment are in progress for some of the proposed smart things. The future work will be deployment and integration with local governing body.

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References

1. Vishvjit Thakar, Smart Water Leakage Detection, Monitoring and Control, INAC- 4, Organized by ISSE -SAC, ISRO, Ahmadabad, 2019.
2. <https://www.isro.gov.in/SatelliteNavigationServices.html>.
3. M.Rashid, Power Electronics - Circuits, Devices and Applications, Pearson Education, 2004.
4. Ned Mohan, Power Electronics: Converter, Applications and Design, Wiley Publications,2005.
5. Ian F. Akyldiz and Ahan Kak, The Internet of Space Things/ Cubesats: A Ubiquitous Cyber Physical System for the connected world, Computer Networks, 150, pp 134-149, Elsevier Publication, 2019.
6. Juan A. Fraire et al, Direct to Satellite IoT- A Survey of the State of the Art and Future Perspectives: Backhauling the IoT Through LEO Satellites, Springer Nature, pp 241-258,2019.
7. <https://www.slscorp.com/smarttraffic>.
8. <https://www.thethingsnetwork.org/docs/lorawan/what-is-lorawan/>
9. <https://www.slscorp.com/smartstreet>